

EFFECT OF BRAND IMAGE ON CUSTOMER BASED BRAND EQUITY (CBBE) OF FAST MOVING CONSUMER GOODS

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to investigate the role of brand image and analyze the effect of brand image on Customer-Based Brand Equity (CBBE) of fast moving consumer goods (FMCG). To accomplish this goal, a structured questionnaire was developed, and the research hypothesis was tested with data collected from the 167 respondents of Madurai city. Findings reveal that brand image has a positive effect on CBBE. The study identifies the impact of brand image and demonstrates that to build effective CBBE, FMCG companies should improve brand image. We have given recommendations to the Brand Managers of FMCG companies based on the outcomes of the study. Limitations and suggestions for future research in this area are provided.

Keywords: Brand Image, Customer Based Brand Equity (CBBE), FMCG, Brand Awareness, Brand Association.

1. Introduction

Customer based brand equity is an essential and key concept for the retail sector. It is most important to know how customer perceives the brands and products in their minds. FMCG brands are making different efforts to identify the factors that improve their brand performance. In specific they encounter issues related to brand building and consumer perception.

Brand is more significant for the FMCG sector because as its influence in purchase decision. The customer chance of preferring the particular brand is based on the immediate recall and association with that brand. So FMCG companies to enhance the brand awareness and brand loyalty of their brands, they analyze the brand enrichment opportunities in the market.

FMCG sector is a rapidly growing due to the increase in standard of living and customer expectation of more comfort. FMCG goods are well packed goods with different categories like personal care products, packed readymade food products, cosmetic products, home care products and beverage like soft drinks and health drinks. Modernisation of house hold in the past two decades gave paved way for increase in consumption of packed goods. This made competition among players of FMCG industry to acquire and retain market share. They are struggling to position their brands in the consumer minds. A brand plays a crucial part in the buying decision of FMCG goods. In order to understand the customer perception and build brand accordingly. The concept of customer based brand equity is used. In the Keller's model of customer based brand equity, brand identify, brand meaning, brand response, brand resonance are the key components.

Our current research aims to find out the effect of brand image on the customer brand equity, brand image is an idea and good thought about the particular brand. Customer exhibit different attitude towards various brands because of their perception about the brand. Brand image is the collection of idea about the brand processed in the buyers mind. The thoughts are generated by the brand attributes they are functional, benefits and emotional benefits of the brand products. Brand image is used by the marketer as a tool to differentiate among competitors product.

2. Literature review

(Khan et al., 2014) studied the causal relationship among dimensions of customer based brand equity and purchase intention. The findings of the study revealed that brand loyalty has more impact on purchase intention that other dimension of brand equity. The results reflects that brand image is the unique feature of the product in the competitive market to differentiate from others. The researcher has recommended that brand image should be included among the measuring factors of the brand

equity.

(Sürücü et al., 2019) analyzed the effect of customer based brand equity on customer loyalty and also the roles of customer satisfaction and trust in hotel industry. The results of their study reveal that customer satisfaction has a positive effect on trust and loyalty. And it also demonstrated that customer based brand equity (CBBE) is a significant factor in building customer loyalty. The study finally suggested that positive brand image is one of the important determinants of CBBE.

(Algharabat et al., 2020) presented a comprehensive study of customer based brand equity in social media. In their study they experimented the influence of customer brand engagement (consumer involvement, consumer participation, and self-expressive brand) on customer based brand equity (CBBE). The study results highlight that consumer involvement has the major impact on customer based engagement. They found that customer based engagement has no positive impact on the brand awareness and perceived quality of the social media page.

(Rodríguez-López et al., 2020) examined the relationship between customer perception of restaurant authenticity and customer based brand equity. They selected two different types of restaurant for their research. The findings of the study revealed that customer based brand equity depends on the authenticity in both food and environment of the restaurant. The research concludes that customer based brand equity (CBBE) is the effect of customer satisfaction and this customer satisfaction is attained because of authenticity.

(Jeon & Yoo, 2021) illustrated a model that brand experience and customer based brand equity (CBBE) are the key factors that could increase the brand loyalty in the grocery sector. The researcher analyzed and identified the influence of brand experience on perceived value and brand loyalty through brand awareness, brand image and perceived quality. The result of the research suggests that brand association, brand image and perceived quality are important factors influencing the perceived value of the brand by the customer.

(Zia et al., 2021) examined the impact of brand loyalty and brand image on brand equity with brand recognition as a mediator. The outcome of the study states that brand loyalty and brand image has some impact on brand equity. Loyalty of the customer towards the brand plays an important role in the consistent growth of the company. The study has put forth brand awareness as a mediator to influence the brand loyalty and brand image.

3. Research Methodology

3.1 objective of the study

The major purpose of the research is to find out whether there is any relationship that exists between brand image and customer based brand equity and the research has another objective to study the association between the demographic factors and customer based brand equity.

3.2 Data collection and sample

In this study convenient sampling methods were used to select the respondents. The respondents are chosen among the FMCG customers in Madurai city. The questionnaire was distributed to the selected respondents. The completed questionnaires are collected back from the respondents. The questionnaires which are completely filled alone have been taken for consideration. By this way questionnaires from 167 respondents are collected and used for this research.

4. Data analysis

4.1. Descriptive results

The Table 1 provides an overview of the demographic profile of the sample respondents taken for the study consideration. It can be seen from the data in the table 1 that 62.3 % of the respondents belong to the female group. It represents that 41.9 % of the respondents are undergraduates and 33.5 % of the respondents are postgraduates. It is apparent from this table that monthly family income for 49.7% of the respondents is less than Rs.30,000 category.

Table 1: Demographic profile of the study, Sample (n = 167)

Demographic characteristics		Frequency	Percentage %
Gender	Male	63	37.7 %

	Female	104	62.3 %
Age	18 -25	71	42.5 %
	26-35	34	20 %
	36-45	28	16.8 %
	Above 45	34	20.4 %
Educational qualification	High school	19	11.4 %
	Undergraduate	70	41.9 %
	Postgraduate	56	33.5 %
	Professional	22	13.2 %
Family income – monthly	Less than rs.30,000	83	49.7 %
	Rs.30,001 – Rs.60,000	54	32.3 %
	More than 60,000	30	18.0 %

4.2. Hypothesis testing

To verify the relationship between the brand image and customer based brand equity ,spearman’s rank correlation test is conducted.

H₀₁ : There is no relationship between brand image and customer based brand equity.H_{a1}: There is a relationship between brand image and customer based brand equity.

Table 2 : Spearman’s rank correlation between brand image and customer based brand equity.

Correlations

		Brand image	CBBE
Spearman's rho	Brand image	1.000	.777**
	Correlation Coefficient		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
	N	167	167
CBBE	Brand image	.777**	1.000
	Correlation Coefficient		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
	N	167	167

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Correlation Coefficient between brand image and customer based brand equity is 0.777 which indicate (0.777 = 0.603) 60.3 % percentage positive relationships exists between brand image and customer based brand equity at 1% significant level.

The chi-square test is conducted to analyze the following hypotheses which results the association between demographic factors and customer based brand equity.

H₀₂ : There is no association between educational qualification and level of CBBE H_{a2}: There is an association between educational qualification and level of CBBE

Table 3 : Chi- Square test for association between education qualification and level of CBBE

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	29.718 ^a	6	.000
Likelihood Ratio	22.700	6	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	10.608	1	.001
N of Valid Cases	167		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 4.66.

Table 4 : cross tabulation of educational qualification and level of CBBE.

Educational Qualification * Level of CBBE Cross tabulation

Count

		Level of CBBE			Total
		Low	Moderate	High	
Educational Qualification	High school	15	3	1	19
	Under graduate	11	47	12	70
	post graduate	9	18	29	56
	professional	6	13	3	22
Total		41	81	45	167

Since P value is less than 0.01, the null hypothesis is rejected at 1 % level of significance. Hence concluded that there is strong association between educational qualification and level of customer based brand equity (CBBE). From the table 4 we can understand that majority of high school qualifiers has low level of CBBE and most of the post graduate qualifiers has high level of CBBE but in undergraduate category many had moderate level of CBBE.

H_{03} : There is no association between monthly family income and level of CBBE H_{a3} : There is an association between monthly family income and level of CBBE

Table 5 : Chi- Square test for association between family income and level of CBBE

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	27.506 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	27.622	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	18.409	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	167		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 7.37.

Table 6 : cross tabulation of family income and level of CBBE.

Family income * Level of CBBE Crosstabulation

Count

		Level of CBBE			Total
		Low	Moderate	High	
Family income	less than 30000	33	33	17	83
	30001 to 60000	6	35	13	54
	more than 60000	2	13	15	30
Total		41	81	45	167

Since P value is less than 0.01, the null hypothesis is rejected at 1 % level of significance. Hence concluded that there is strong association between Family income (monthly) and level of customer based brand equity (CBBE). From the table 6 we can understand that majority of respondents in the family income (monthly) more than rs.60,000 category has high level of CBBE and most of the respondents in rs.30,000 to rs.60,000 category has moderate level of CBBE than in the category of less than rs.30,000 most of the respondents lies in the both low and moderate level of CBBE.

5. Results of research

5.1. Discussion and conclusions of results

An initial objective of the research was to identify the effect of brand image on customer based brand equity. From the results of the study we can come to the conclusion that there is a positive correlation between brand image and customer based brand equity (CBBE). The study also investigated the demographic characteristics and its association with customer based brand equity (CBBE). The research can be summarized that educational qualification and family income of the customer also affects the customer attitude towards the brand. These demographic factors influence the brand association and brand identity which in turn influence brand choice and preference during purchase of the FMCG goods.

5.2. Managerial implications

FMCG sector is the most competitive in the retail market segment. The heavy competition is because of its market potential and enhanced growth. The evidence from this research suggests that to overcome this tough competition among the FMCG players, FMCG companies should concentrate on the improvisation of brand image. Brand image is most significant factor among the brand building components. This study confirms the importance of the brand image that portrayed in previous researches. Marketers can reinforce their brand image by advertising the brand's commitment and emotional connect with the customers. It could help to increase the emotional attachment and customers engagement with the brands

5.3. Limitations and future research

The scope of the study limited in terms of number of data collected from the respondents next to that geographic location considered for the research. Second limitation of the study is it considered analysing the brand image effect on customer based brand equity. A Further research shall be undertaken to explore and analyze the impact of perceived quality, price and brand loyalty on customer based brand equity of fast moving consumer goods.

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